

Challenges facing the administration of ICT infrastructural facilities in public primary schools in Nigeria

Deborah Jegede¹

Post Graduate Student, University of Abuja, Nigeria
Email: Jegededeborah30@gmail.com

Lydia Abashi Ebio

Federal University Wukari, Nigeria
Email: lydiaabashi54@gmail.com

Abigail Ifeomal Iroegbu

Federal University Wukari, Taraba State, Nigeria, Public Primary Schools,
Email: Iroegbuabigail@gmail.com

Abstract: The paper examines the challenges preventing effective administration of ICT facilities in the Nigerian basic schools. The paper identified inadequate funding of ICT programs, inadequate ICT infrastructural facilities, shortage of ICT manpower, unstable power supply, high cost of ICT facilities and poor network services, and poor implementation of ICT policies in basic schools. To address these challenges, the paper recommended the following: adequate funding of Computer education program, provision of ICT facilities, subsidize the cost of ICT facilities, implement the ICT policies on education, capacity development for teachers and provision of constant electricity and internet services.

Keywords: Basic Schools, Challenges, ICT facilities, ICT Infrastructural facilities.

Introduction:

Primary education is the bedrock on which other levels of education are built. The National Policy on Education (2004) refers to it as “Education given in an institution for children” normally aged 6-11. This is the level that prepares pupils for Secondary Education. It is necessary that basic skills are inculcated into learners as specified in the objectives.

The National Policy on Education (2004) stated the objectives of primary education as follows:

- i. The inculcation of permanent literacy and numeracy and the ability to communicate effectively.
- ii. The laying of a sound basis for scientific and reflective thinking;
- iii. Citizenship education as a basis for effective participation in and contribution to the life of the society.
- iv. Character and moral training and the development of sound attitudes;
- v. Developing in the child the ability to adapt to his changing environment;
- vi. Giving the child opportunity for developing manipulative skills that will enable him to function effectively in the society within the limits of his capacity and;

¹ Corresponding author

- vii. Providing basic tools for further educational advancement including preparation for trades and crafts of the locality.

Shehu and Na-allah, (2015) It is important to note that, the philosophy behind Basic Education in Nigeria is to provide an opportunity for every learner who has successfully completed the nine years of continuous Basic Education schooling, should have acquired sufficient level of literacy, numeracy, manipulative, communicative and life-long skills as well as ethical, moral and civic values needed for laying a solid foundation for life-long learning as a basis for scientific and reflective thinking. The basic education curriculum is structured into three levels of operation namely; lower basic education curriculum (primary 1-3), middle basic education curriculum (primary 4-6), and upper basic education curriculum (JS1-3). Both the national policy on education and the national policy on information and communication technologies (ICT) in education have clearly stated the position of the government on the place and role of ICTs in education, which is expected to guide and propel teachers to apply ICTs in the basic education classrooms. It is pertinent to note that, the current state of primary schools in Nigeria is not favorable for the attainment of the set objectives for basic education. Although there are clear pieces of evidence of infrastructural improvement and increased access to at all levels of education in Nigeria with the introduction of universal basic education program (UBE), much is still desired, because instructional resources including teaching manpower are still grossly inadequate with untrained personnel, non-availability of computers, computer laboratories and other ICT facilities like electricity and internet connectivity in most public primary schools in Nigeria.

In Nigerian basic Schools, the curriculum covers the following programs English, Mathematics, the Nigerian language, basic science and technology, religion and national values, and cultural and creative arts, Arabic language (optional). Pre-vocational studies (home economics, agriculture, and entrepreneurship) and the French language are introduced in grade 4.

Oyekanmi, (2016) cited Njoku, (2011) Submitted that technology for educational purposes will enable students and teachers to build a new educational environment by using tools that not only process information but also allow the learner to investigate, manipulate, test and extend knowledge. Basic Technology which was previously known as Introductory Technology was structured to assist learners to develop interest in technology. It is a subject offered in Upper Basic Schools in Nigeria which introduces students to basic rudiment of technology (Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council, 2007). It is one of the core subjects to be offered by all students as stated in the curriculum for Upper Basic Schools in Nigeria. Basic Technology is regarded as one of the subjects through which the pivot of the significance of all developed nations rotates (Oyekanmi, 2016, Bamiro & Akuru, 2010).

The main objectives of teaching Basic Technology as stated by NERDC (2007) are to inculcate technology literacy, expose students to the world of work to match their talents, and inculcate a positive attitude towards work as a source of human livelihood and power. Basic Technology which is a core subject of 9-3-4 System of Education in Nigeria today involves the academic and practical study of materials. This subject is expected to sharpen the appetite of learners for skill subjects. Basic Technology is also an integrated study of skills subjects such as woodwork, metalwork, building technology, auto mechanic, electrical/electronic, ceramics and technical drawing, you and technology (Oyekanmi, 2016, Olaniyan & Lucas, 2008).

The Nigerian government has integrated Information Communication Technology (ICT) into the Nigerian educational system. This made for the inclusion of Information Communication Technology (ICT) policies in the National policy on education. The National policies of education

recognize the prominent role of ICTs in the modern world and integrated ICTs into education in Nigeria. For full implementation of ICT education and integration into all the educational systems the policies stated that the government will provide necessary infrastructure and training for the integration of ICTs in all educational institutions.

The achievement of the basic education goals and ICT policies for basic education depends on the effectiveness of the school administration. The school administration is key to the success of any educational policies because they are the administrative power behind the planning and formulation of policies for the smooth implementation of the program at the school level. School administration deals with the arrangement of various educational resources to realize the set objectives of the school. In these modern days, information and communication technology facilities are one of the crucial educational resources that school administrators need to successfully implement the school's program especially when it relates to the Computer program in the Schools. Administration of ICT facilities in educational institutions is posing a lot of challenges. This article examines the challenges facing the administration of ICT infrastructural facilities in Public Primary Schools in Nigeria.

Concept of Information Communication Technology (ICT):

United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO, 2005) viewed ICT as a combination of all the computers, telecommunication, and media technologies. They are also electronic technologies used for accessing, processing, gathering, manipulating, and presenting or communicating information in the education system. ICT is defined by Ayannuga (2009) as the marriage that exists between computer system and communication which can be described as the use of computer-based technology and internet to make information and communication services available to a greater number of users.

Uwabueze & Ozioko (2011) sees information and communication technology as a set of tools that help a person work with information and perform tasks related to the information process. Unwin, (2004) observed that ICT has improved the value of education by providing access to a great variety of educational resources and by enabling participatory pedagogies. It also improves the management of education through more efficient administrative processes, including human resource management, monitoring and evaluation, and resource sharing.

The United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization (UNESCO, 2013) stated that ICT can contribute to universal access to education, equity in education, the delivery of quality learning and teaching, teachers' professional development, efficient management, governance, and administration. Patrick and Brenda (2018) write that ICT is not just the bloom of the education system, but also the primary and secondary options required to improve effective and meaningful interaction between teachers and students of secondary schools. It has the power to make students enjoy things that they would normally find time-consuming and difficult because it involves practical teaching and student-centered and not teachers talking and writing on the chalkboard and student copying from the chalkboard into their notebook without engaging in practical teaching which makes learning boring. ICT is a teaching tool that improves the quality of secondary school student's education and support teachers' work. ICT usage in teaching in public secondary schools will aid effective teachings and learning and help the students acquire necessary skills that will enable them to contribute to the growth, improvement, and development of the nation socially and economically.

Patrick and Brenda (2018) the place of the computer in the use of ICT in teaching cannot be overemphasized. A computer can be defined as an electronic machine that can accept data as input, processes the data, and produces the result as output through a set of instructions called program. Computer Studies on the other hand is the study of the computer which includes computer hardware and software but not how to use the computer. It is seen as a room (Computer/ICT laboratory) filled with treasures (ICT facilities) and can be assessed by the computer studies teachers. The teachers can take their students into the treasure room and show them the different treasures inside the treasure room and how they operate but not how to use the treasures.

Abubakar (2016) considering its part of education in national advancement and the expansion in the populace in schools nowadays, the utilization of computers in instruction and learning process gets to be basic. This is on the grounds that its acceptance by educators will upgrade the system of instruction delivery to a better one. ICT will also help issues like effective classroom management, collaborative learning, self-study, course/subject organization, and enhance effective communication between peers, teachers, and student-teacher. In today's modern-day teaching, students partake actively and vigorously in the process unlike before where a teacher will stand in front of a class and giving lectures to students without them contributing to the subject or topic (Abubakar 2016 cited Ajayi, 2008).

The different ICT gadgets utilized during instruction delivery and learning in schools and colleges as indicated by Ofodu (2007) in Abubakar (2016) includes incorporating audio sets, TV, PCs projectors Optical fiber cables, Telephones, Mobile devices, Handhold devices, Fax machines, Internet, Intranet, CD-ROM, PPT slides, electronic board, digital multi-media, video/VCD, DVD, machines, etc. It creates the impression that some of these gadgets are not adequately accommodated teaching and learning in the Nigerian government post-primary schools. We also have PC based operation/system, video and audio conferencing, LAN, www, and Computer-Assisted Instruction (CAI).

Concept of Educational Administration:

Noun (2008) the concept of educational administration may not be totally different from what we are familiar with the concept of administration. In Nigeria, education at different levels has its objectives as stated in the National Policy on Education, the most important of the objectives that cut across all the levels of education is teaching and learning. It is the function of the school to produce educated and enlightened human beings who would be able to contribute positively to the development of society.

Noun (2008) Administration is very germane to the realization of the school's objectives – indeed, the success of the school system depends largely on the administration of the school is handled. The teachers, students, non-teaching staff, and resources must be efficiently arranged, monitored, and controlled so that they would work harmoniously according to (educational plan).

The National Policy on Education (2004) emphasizes the success of the entire educational system on proper planning, efficient administration, and adequate funding. School administration is the process by which principles, methods, and practices of administration are applied in educational institutions to establish, maintain, and develop such institutions in line with the goals of the institutions.

In modern-day educational administration, there are many educational resources that are needed for effective school administration and these resources include teachers, non-teaching staff, that is on the side of human resources while the materials resources include teaching aids, school plants, financial resources, ICT facilities, etc.

ICT facilities in school administration refer to the effective and efficient utilization of ICT facilities to achieve the objectives of the school. It is the systematic process of utilizing ICT facilities to attain the aims and objectives of teaching and learning in the educational system. Effective administration of ICT facilities depends on the availability of the ICT facilities in the educational institutions.

Challenges preventing Effective Administration of ICT infrastructural facilities in Nigerian Basic Schools:

The following are the challenges facing the administration of ICT Infrastructural facilities in public primary schools in Nigeria; inadequate funding of ICT program, inadequate ICT infrastructural facilities, shortage of ICT manpower, unstable power supply, high cost of ICT facilities and poor network services, poor implementation of ICT policies in basic schools and poor ICT literacy.

- i. **Inadequate Funding of ICT programme:** Funding is the key to the successful implementation of ICT programs in the educational institution. The budgetary allocation for the implementation of computer education is inadequate in the basic schools and this is affecting the utilization of ICT facilities in the basics schools. To run or operate a computer system needs a lot of financial resources. School administrators of basic schools are not provided with adequate funds to manage the various ICF infrastructural under their cares.
- ii. **Inadequate ICT Infrastructural Facilities:** Odera (2012) reported in her research five problems confronting the implementation of ICT in Education thus: non-availability of computers or inadequate supply of computers in most of the secondary schools; lack of proper teacher training to help them integrate computers into teaching and learning; lack of time to incorporate computers into the subject being taught; inadequate or lack of physical facilities to enable schools to introduce computer education and lack of relevant software. These highlighted factors had expressed other problems that can be attributed to poor implementation of computer education in this nation. Abubakar (2016) The low rate in the adaptation and application of the new technology especially in the public schools in north-eastern Nigerian is attributed to several factors which include inadequate ICT 5 facilities in the schools, poor ICT policies, limited information infrastructures, poor perceptions of using ICT in education among teachers, students, and the school administrators. This proposed the quantity of PCs accessible in schools is insufficient for the students' populace (Stephen, 2013) Abubakar (2016) cited Idoko and Ademu (2010) who discovered that availability of ICT is often one of the most critical impediments to technology acceptance and integration in teaching and learning. They demonstrated that there is a persistent necessity for more ICT facilities if a nation is to effectively incorporate ICT into its public collages.

- iii. **Shortage of ICT Manpower:** The effective utilization of ICT facilities depends largely on the teacher's and students' capacity to use the ICT facilities to aid in teaching and learning. The application of ICT facilities in the educational institutions depends largely on the numbers of ICT instructors or teachers the schools are having at a particular time. Inadequate ICT manpower in educational institutions is affecting the effective utilization of ICT facilities in schools. Research has it that shortage of professional ICT teachers is preventing the effective implementation of Computer education in schools in Nigeria.
- iv. **Unstable Power Supply:** Nigeria a developing country is facing the challenge of providing adequate power for its citizens. The inability of the government to provide constant electricity and to ensure every nook and crannies access electricity is affecting the utilization of ICT facilities in the Nigerian basic schools. Patrick and Brenda (2018) cited Mungai, (2011) observed that many schools are not yet connected to electricity especially in developing countries, Nigeria inclusive. In such countries, the government has not been able to connect all parts of the country to the national electrical grid. Consequently, those schools that fall under such areas are left handicapped and may not be able to offer computer studies. According to Mohammed and Yarinchi (2013), the inadequate power supply is one of the major problems confronting the teaching and learning process in Nigeria with particular reference to computers among others as it brings about digression, failure to achieve the desired goals, and objectives in time. Agyeman (2007), submitted that about 40% of Nigerians enjoy electricity from the national grid, however, the electric power supply is sporadic, and several communities in the urban areas lack electric power and those rural communities are worse off because of the absence of infrastructures.
- v. **High Cost of ICT Facilities:** The high cost of ICT facilities is also responsible for poor administration of ICT in the Nigerian basic schools because many teachers and students cannot afford to buy the various ICT facilities they needed to support teaching and learning in the classroom. Adomi (2006) also identifies cost as one of the factors which influence the provision and use of ICT services, indicating that the cost of computers is too high for many to afford. Brakel and Chiseuga (2003) observe that monthly internet rates are exorbitant and the charges for satellite television are unaffordable for most people in Africa. The high cost of ICT facilities has made it difficult for Nigerian Secondary Schools to acquire and install ICT facilities for the use of teachers and students (Adomi and Kpangan, 2010). The cost was also identified as a challenge facing the implementation of computer education in Kenya secondary schools (Mungai, 2011). Oyekanmi, (2016) cited Alesinloye (2006) reported in his survey that, cost of obtaining a computer, weak infrastructure, lack of skills, lack of relevant software, and limited access to the internet are the factors impeding the successful use of Information and Communication Technology in Nigerian education. This is rightly observed, presently, the nation has only crude oil as her major exporting goods, while machinery like cars, computers, and the likes are the country major importing goods. Unfortunately, this is a great discouragement to the adoption of computer in the country.

- vi. **Poor Network Services:** Poor Network service or poor internet service is another problem preventing effective administration of ICT facilities in basic school for delivering teaching and learning. Alesinloye (2006) observed that limitation to internet access. This is not untrue about the nation, higher institutions in Nigeria suffer poor or no internet access while majority of the country's secondary schools have no access to internet at all. Lack of skills is also an obvious factor that needs attention in the proper implementation of computer education in the nation.
- vii. **Poor Policy Implementation:** Poor policy implementation in Nigeria is another factor responsible for the poor application of ICT facilities for the teaching and learning process in all the basic schools in Nigeria. Patrick and Brenda (2018) cited Laaria, (2013). Since the 1980s implementation of ICT in schools has been compulsory in the developed nations. This is not so in developing nations such as Nigeria, where implementation is considerably more recent, small-scale and experimental. It is, however, universally acknowledged that implementation of ICT in schools has progressed in the nearly identical patterns, from the formulation of policies, attainment of basic computer skills, computer-aided teaching and learning, communications, and research, to usage in every subject. While other countries have achieved over 41% implementation of ICT in secondary schools, the percentage in African schools remains very small. Oyekanmi, (2016) observed that in the report that the common factor that tends to inhibit the proper implementation of Information and Communication Technology into secondary schools has clearly been attributed to the failure of the government to play their own unquantifiable part by properly equipping the learning materials (the teachers inclusive). Oyekanmi, (2016) cited Bukaliya and Mubika (2012) concluded in their report on the factors militating against the introduction of computer education in secondary schools, highlighted two major factors that are impeding computer education in secondary schools as follow; no budgets for computer procurement in the majority of schools and funds were inadequate for computer procurement as central government did not avail finances for computer procurement.
- viii. **Poor ICT Literacy:** Dzionu (2010) Submitted that in many African countries, lack of well-trained teachers and low levels of teachers' ICT skill and knowledge has been recognized as a major obstacle in the implementation of ICT in schools. Abubakar (2016) The compelling usage of ICT in instruction and learning relies on upon the accessibility of these facilities and the educators' capability in utilizing them. Observation has shown that there are limited functional ICT facilities in most Nigeria public schools especially those in the rural areas. This in turn hinders the urge to use them by the students for learning. Also, lack of adequate computer literate from the site of instructors, sporadic power supply, and insufficient financial support are another set of deterrent militating against successful usage of ICT facilities and resources in government-owned institutions.

Recommendations:

Based on the challenges identified and discussed above, to address the issues raised regarding the challenges preventing effective administration of ICT facilities in Nigerian basic schools. This paper, therefore, recommends the following: adequate funding of Computer

education program, provision of ICT facilities, subsidize the cost of ICT facilities, implement the ICT policies on education, capacity development for teachers and provision of constant electricity and internet services:

- i. **Adequate Funding for Computer Education Programme:** The government should increase the funding of ICT education in all the basic schools across the country.
- ii. **Provision of ICT facilities:** The government should provide more ICT facilities to all the basic schools to enable the schools to deploy ICT facilities for teaching and learning in the classroom.
- iii. **Subsidize the cost of ICT facilities:** The government should subsidy ICT facilities for teachers and students to enable teachers and students to buy their personal systems.
- iv. **Implement the ICT policies on education:** The national policy on information and communication technology in education thrust should be well implemented beyond mere policy statement.
- v. **Capacity Development for Teachers:** Capacity development programs should be provided for basic school teachers to enable them to use ICT facilities for teaching in their various schools.
- vi. **Provision of Constant Electricity and Internet Services:** The government should ensure that educational institutions in the country especially the basic school are provided with constant power supply and internet services.
- vii. **Employment of ICT Instructors:** The government should employ more ICT teachers and deploy them to basic schools where their services are urgently needed.

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